

Title

The influence of Italian cinema on Iranian cinema from the 80's to the present.

Emphasizing the works of two generations of Iranian filmmakers : *Abbas Kiarostami* and *Asghar Farhadi*

Author

GELAREH HAJMOUSA

Affiliation

Graduate Researcher, Faculty of literature and Philosophy, Sapienza university of Rome, Italy

Abstract

Social realism is used as a way to illustrate social problems and glitches in cinema in parallel with other artistic movements. One of the most important kinds of this cinema has been formed in Italy. Social realism in Italy has attracted the attention of many countries because of the reality of post-war lifetime. The avoidance of Hollywood filmmaking, the lack of use of professional actors, the use of long shots and real locations are its most important features. Iran's cinema has always been influenced by the Italian cinema. At the same time as the revolution and war broke out, in Iranian filmmakers there was a tendency towards Italian cinema, which was able to present a kind of Iranian realism in the world of cinema. Iranian Cinema, with the formation of the new wave of production, has begun in the field of producing social films that continued until today. The cinema of Iranian social realism in the 1980s and 90s was formed under the influence of war and after-war implications, and its main feature includes films directed by *Abbas Kiarostami* that the impact of Italian cinema can be recognized primarily. Also, the social cinema of the first decade of the second millennium, which is one of the most important periods of social realism in Iran's cinema, has also led to the emergence of a new and different social cinema with the advent of young filmmakers such as the Oscar winner, *Asghar Farhadi*, which is deep-rooted from Italian cinema. In this article, we have tried to show the effect of Italian cinema on Iranian cinema by relying on the works of the mentioned filmmakers and studying on the similarities and differences between Iranian and Italian cinema in the field of social realism.

Keywords: Italian neorealism, Iranian cinema, Abbas Kiarostami, Asghar Farhadi, social realism, film studies

Introduction

The cinema, as the seventh art, was initially formed on the basis of realism and the perception of what was really seen. Gradually, the desire for realism in the field of cinema diminished in filmmakers, since political and social developments have a direct impact on the country's cultural and artistic arena. The emergence of World War II as one of the most important occurrences in that era has caused a dramatic change in the field of cinema. In the same period, due to the formation of special conditions, the largest post-war cinematic movement was formed. In other words, after World War II, the desire for social realism in the field of cinema was increased and became institutionalized as one of the most important styles. The dilemmas and destruction of World War II as well as the bad economic conditions of the people prepared the territory for realistic films. So cinema has been challenging internal and war-related problems. So for the first

time, the realities within the public became the subject of films. A serious pioneering social realism in the cinema was Italy, which due to the circumstances, was able to offer films in the form of social realism with new and inclusive topics. These films also influenced the cinema of other countries. The form and effect of Italian cinema on the social cinema of the world were such that the root of social realism in cinema was introduced by Italy ¹.

Iran's cinema, like the cinema of the world, has had its ups and downs from the very beginning, and it has always been subject due to political, economic and social changes. The impact of Italian cinema has had a long history on Iranian cinema. Some of the best Iranian filmmakers were influenced by philosophical insights and Italian style. Also, local and foreign critics were also the main factor influenced by Italian cinema before the Iran's revolution (*the New Wave*) and after the revolution (*art films*). The introduction and screening of Italian films in Iran, made the new desire in filmmakers and audiences. The war and the Islamic Revolution in Iran once again brought about widespread changes in the field of art, which had led to the formation of new trends in line with the political and social movements. The process of these changes continued until the 1980s, and in the 90's in the field of social realism with the presence of young and educated young filmmakers, the formation of a standard cinema with different style and content was developed. Due to the importance of this type of cinema and audience-centeredness, as well as the type of social reality presentation on the screen, its thematic and facets aspects should be explained. For this reason, this cinema requires a comprehensive study. In this article, by explaining the linguistic and temporal features of social realism in Italian cinema, its impact on Iranian cinema has been studied. Along with the roots of social realism in the cinema of Iran will be discussed ².

Social realism

One of the definitions given in relation to social realism is “an art that deals with issues and topics related to the work and life of the laborers, and has political and social content” ³. These artists were trying to portray the society, racial inequities, economic hardship in an unpolished image in everyday life, and in this way they generally show the working class as a hero.

This artistic movement has a critical point of view of the artists about the situation of their community and the subject of each one refers to one of the problems encountered by society. The changes in society are likely to be effective in shaping artistic changes by changing the cultural context of the community. Also, environmental changes provide the necessary resources for the emergence of new innovative cultural-artistic movements.

¹ Huaco, George. *Sociology of Film Art*. Publisher: Basic Books. October, 1965

² Mohammad Kashi, Sabereh. *Realism in Iranian cinema*. Journal of the Moon of art. No. 95, 2006

³ Pakbaz, Royan. *Encyclopedia of Art*. Eighth Edition, Tehran: Contemporary Culture. 2009

The origin of social realism in the cinema

The realism movement has involved in all the arts before entering to the cinema. Realism sometimes got new meanings in dealing with a camcorder as a world recorder. *Susan Hayward* believes, “As far as the camcorder is concerned, understanding why the camera is considered a natural tool for realism is not difficult. The film turns the past to the presence. It shows the reality on the screen”. It opens up an immediate and realistic perspective of the real world by offering characters and their environment in front of our eyes. Realism in the film acts both at the level of narrative and at the virtual level. Social realism can be labeled as a range of films that reflect society. These films are generally formed by the emergence of specific political-social conditions or in response to existing conditions. For example, after the Second World War, Americans demanded a more realistic view of the country that can be found in the crowd of *Film Noir*. In general, post-war social, political and economic developments bring people to reality. This change in perspective is also important in a comprehensive and global arts like cinema. From that time on, the fantasy cinema was slowly disappeared as people liked films that appeal to the social facts. The clashes in communities as well as the audience's experience make the films more acceptable and the criticisms of the film about the conditions of the society make the audience happy ⁴. The realist films in cinema are divided into two major parts of documentary films and social realism films. But in discussing realism in cinema, the approach of this research is to films that mean to create a realistic image of society. The features of these films include especially, the conflicts between the individual and society, and the analysis of individuals in particular environments ⁵.

Cinema of Italy and social realism

The first movement in Italy, followed by British Free Cinema and The New Wave of the United Kingdom, and eventually a disconcerting group of Cinéma Vérité (a style of film-making characterized by realistic) in France. But the biggest change in the cinema of social realism is after World War II that is the most influential post-war cinematic style in the world of cinema. The main films of this movement related to Italian cinema. Although due to political and social conditions may have emerged, but most of the cinema historians believed that its success is because of its innovations in the form of the film ⁶.

The films were not pre-designed. Professional actors were not used and was directly connected to social reality, event, streets and open spaces. First, this cinema displayed a daily life. And then spoke about social problems in post-war time of Italy.

⁴ Hayward, Susan. *Cinema studies: The key concepts*. Publisher: Routledge; 4th edition. February, 2013

⁵ Eftekhari, Zahra. *Study of the Origins of the Appearance of Neorealist-Critical Cinema in Iran after the Revolution*. Art Research, Tehran: Art University. 2007

⁶ Thompson, Kristin. Bordwell, David. *Storia del cinema*. Publisher: McGraw-Hill higher education; 9th edition. January 2010

Two major factors are contributed to the formation of the social realism movement in Italy. The first was the World War II and the disappearance of Italian cinema infrastructure, as well as the bad situation of the people that attracted the attention of the filmmakers to the consequences of the war. The second factor was the influence of directors of French poetry realism, especially *Jean Renoir*, on Italian filmmakers ⁷. David Bordwell believes that another reason for the formation of social realism is the return to modernism. Modernist filmmakers were trying to reveal the unpleasant facts of the social class ⁸. The return to modernism and the transformation of opinion cannot be without changes within a community. Italy's filmmakers displayed a reflection of their society in their films. *George Huaco* offers the best definition of reality in this cinema. In his opinion, "the reality is poverty, unemployment and hunger, single and unemployed industrial workers, hungry farmers and fishermen and very young or very old, poor and helpless people, and immigrant workers. Prostitution, theft, suicide and murder are the main themes of these films, which are often presented as a result of poverty and unemployment and hunger" ⁹. A very critical interpretation of these films was widely welcomed since the people themselves were involved and experienced these topics. These filmmakers considered everyday life as the most real thing everyone involved with and narrated their stories from it. What distinguishes neo-realism from other realistic styles is the way of representing reality based on what has happened, relying on simplicity and critical attitude.

Cinema of Iran and social realism

Looking at the history of Iran's cinema and analyzing the factors involved in the formation of the realism wave, prove that four factors led to the beginning of realism in Iran's cinema. These factors are: the left (political group) intellectuals, the critique of criticism with popular films, the Stream of documentary cinema, and the effects of Italian cinema. The effects of the realist cinema of the world, especially Italy, formed the foundations of the realist cinema of Iran. Social realism, even if it contains the issues of the day, is idealistic towards the future, and the future of cinema in Iran after these films is a contradictory but prominent reality. This cinema, which in Iran is briefly called "social cinema", can be traced back to the history of the cinema before and after the 1978 revolution and war. In this period, filmmakers have chosen themes that are rooted in political and social realities. They used documentary subjects, they did sound recording on the scene, and they had non-professional actors. They also tried to use of local dialects as an important element to be close to the reality. By these efforts they tried to bring the films closer to the realist realm ¹⁰.

⁷ Nowell-Smith, Geoffrey. *The oxford history of world cinema*. Publisher: oxford University press. 17th edition. February 1999

⁸ Thompson, Kristin. Bordwell, David. *Storia del cinema*. Publisher: McGraw-Hill higher education; 9th edition. January 2010.

⁹ Huaco, George. *Sociology of film art*. Publisher: Basic Books. October 1965. P:26

¹⁰ Mohammad Kashi, Sabereh. *Realism in Iranian cinema*. Journal of the Moon of art. No. 95, 2006

Characteristics and common themes of social realism in cinema of Italy and Iran

Although the features of the style of social realism in the cinema were not new, but in the context of the story, these films opened up new areas. Occasionally, films are widely based on the crash and accidental element. Social realism has made it easier to simplify the story. Often the result of events is not told to us either. One feature of Italian social realism is "the future of the unknown" at the end of the film. The tendency of social realism to cross-sectional plotting and indefinite narratives has made many films, unlike Hollywood cinema, endless ¹¹. The social realism uses the ordinary people instead of the professional actors, both in terms of the impact of the Expressions and the actors appearing as heroes. They could not come out of their world and become the hero of another world. This brought the simplicity and honesty of expression to the film which was the main power of realism. Social realism does not look at individual history, but contemplates social history. For example, women who suffer from the effects of the war, the soldiers who returned from the war, and the poor people who wish to live in peace, they all together make a group ¹². At the same time, the filming should be a documentary style, with natural light and a camera on the hand. As a result, cinema is supposed to be a slice of everyday life.

In the study of Iranian and Italian cinema, we conclude that the subject of war is one of the factors that brought changes in the cinema of these two countries. During the war in Iran, and since 1984, institutions created war films. Although the war itself was a social reality, but what is more about social realism is the aftermath of the war. Consequences such as "immigration, moral issues, conflicts between two types of political views, consequences of chemical weapons, and changes of political, psychological and social values. Changing the war films on these issues was due to the distance from the war and the criticality of the post-war Iran and Italy society ¹³. War movies were mostly three categories: 1) Films about Rangers and their missions, 2) On the mission of the people which the story began with a crisis, and eventually, despite the death of the heroes, the crisis would become equilibrium, 3) The films that were related to the effects of the war ¹⁴. The family is the first base of the stability of individual personality. In the real social cinema, the subject of the family has been used in many ways. Divorce and separation and its consequences, social harm and its devastating effects on the family, addiction and economic problems for the family are among the most important tendencies of filmmakers in making their films. The cinematic consequences of war in the field of family cinema pay particular attention ¹⁵.

¹¹ Thompson, K. Bordwell, D. *Film art: an introduction*. Publisher: McGraw-Hill; 4th edition. February 2014. P: 424-505

¹² Verdone, M. *Le avanguardie storiche del cinema*. Torino: Societa editrice internazionale, 1977

¹³ Talebi Nejad, A. *In the presence of the cinema*. First Printing, Tehran: Farabi Publishing. 1998

¹⁴ Farasati, M. *War and Peace*. Association of Revolutionary and Holy Defense Cinema. First Edition, 2000

¹⁵ Talebi Nejad, Ahmad. *Analytical Date of the Post-Revolutionary Cinema*. Tehran: Farabi Publishing. 1998

Social Realism and *Abbas Kiarostami* (1940, Iran – 2016, France)

General Characteristics of *Kiarostami*'s cinema

The style of Italian cinema is keenly featured in *Kiarostami*'s early short films such as “*the bread and alley*” (1970) and “*The traveler*” (1974). In these films, his actors are ordinary people in a pursuit of real life or overcoming a mistake to prove themselves. Under the influence of the Italian social realism style, almost all of his films were filmed on the scene of the city with using the natural light and usage of simple dialects in the local language. The filmmaking style was mainly composed of long-distance views. His films were dealing with social issues and the ethics of realism and neo-realism. His cinema is characterized by the novel opinions, the uncertainties of reality and his compliance with realism. The anti-idealist and violent structure of *Kiarostami* includes self-referencing, referring to his own writings and the sarcastic mix of imagination and reality¹⁶. Part of the ambiguity of *Kiarostami*'s works partly influenced by Iranian psychological tendency toward concealment. Instead of using clarity, Iranians have learned to say things in such a way that seem it has never been said. The works of *Kiarostami* are wrapped in dialogues and this is not only specific to the film's design, character, and subject but it also affects its visual features.

***Kiarostami*'s filming method**

Kiarostami is well-known as a socialist director. He worked with professional filmmakers in all his films. It seems that the director has been able to smartly enrich his cinema with repetitive motifs. *Kiarostami* used continuous filming and editing to diminish the use of classical cinematic techniques. Many of his films, such as “*Taste of Cherry*” (1997), in which a driver and a passenger are in a moving car, have been filming for long. But when changing the view between the two characters inside the car, it never takes a look at the players behind the shoulder to display them at the same time in a visual range. *Kiarostami* said in an interview that while shooting these scenes, there were never a driver and passenger at the same time in the car. Every time the filming was took place, *Kiarostami* sat in the position of another person's place. In this clever change of the codes of realism and neo-realism, actors have to react not to the other actor, but to the director, which compromises *Kiarostami*'s compilation of control over the individual scenes in the film. Therefore, improvisation and the occasional visualization of his works, which binds him to social realism films in Italy, is unrealistic. However, the film is largely improvised, because *Kiarostami* did not use the script in its traditional sense and did not use dialogue written for cast. The method of filming, which is one of the main foundations of classical realism, usually involves depictions from the back of the shoulder of the cast, acquaints the audience with characters by sewing them to the world (sewing theory).

¹⁶ Margulies, Ivone. *Abbas Kiarostami*. Princeton University. Retrieved 23 February 2007.

Kiarostami's little use of these elements, by combining them with other cinematic techniques, makes his films social, realistic, and even educational. The filmmaking style of *Kiarostami* reveals his mentality more than the mentality of the characters in his work. For this reason, his films have a large attraction for audiences, especially non-Iranians. *Kiarostami* by removing the boundary between the filmmaker and the audience, places the filmmaking process in his stories and places the focus from the characters to the camera ¹⁷.

“*Where is the friend's home?*” (*Abbas Kiarostami, 1987*) is one of the *Kiarostami's* most famous films, which is influenced by Italian cinema. *Mohammad Reza*, a rural student, is punished by his teacher because he did not do his homework. The teacher says if he does not do the homework in his notebook, he will be thrown out of class. *Ahmad*, a *Mohammad Reza's* classmate who lives in the adjacent village, at home finds that the notebook of *Mohammad Reza*, which is like his own notebook, has been mistakenly taken home by himself. *Ahmad* decides to bring the notebook to his friend. But he does not succeed in finding his home and eventually returns home due to the darkness. Tomorrow in the school, it turns out that *Ahmad* has done his friend's homework to prevent him from punishment. In the Western publications modern Iranian cinema is called the post-neorealist which is considered as an extension of the Italian cinema ¹⁸. His films, far from any clumsiness, while simplicity and humility, provide a neutral camera view to western audiences to see the social life of people in one of the villages of Iran. *Kiarostami* said in an interview: “I do not see any similarities between myself and others, except the influence of Italian cinema. In addition, the situation that emerged after the Iran-Iraq war in Iran is very similar to the one that existed in Italy”. Many critics disapproved *Kiarostami*, that in the midst of the Iran-Iraq War, instead of addressing the war and the consequences of its destruction, he showed useless theatrical conflict. But it seems *Kiarostami's* response to social events is a profound approach.

Islamic Revolution of Iran had its intellectual foundation on religion, tradition and Islamic-Iranian culture and strongly denied the values of the West. This led to the movement in art and culture. This movement did not grow in music and painting, but it was encountered in the world with a global reflection regards Iranian cinema. After the revolution, the most important definition given to the cinema was consistent with Islamic. But *Kiarostami*, may had unknowingly tried to approach the essence of life and worldview of the people of Iran. One of the most important influences and similarities of Italian cinema with *Kiarostami's* cinema is the use of non-professional actors. The success of “*Where's the friend's home?*” lies in the presence of actors in similar roles to their true character. In this film, two brothers named *Babak* and *Ahmad Ahmadpoo*, with the guidance of *Kiarostami*, play their roles so skillfully as if they were merged with their roles based on *Sergeyevich Stanislavski's* theories.

¹⁷ Mudede, Charles. *Kiarostami's genius style*. The stranger. 1999

¹⁸ Mohammad Kashi, Sabereh. *Realism in Iranian cinema*. Journal of the Moon of art. No. 95, 2006

Kiarostami said: "When we work with a non-professional actor, we must accept our film will be the director / actor's film. Because they interfere in all our work. Sometimes we have to necessarily shift the right lens and ourselves to the extent that they cannot control themselves on the scene. Therefore, they interfere with directing, they change the dialogue and adjust it to their own culture and it's good to do that. I cannot write a dialogue instead of an employee, worker, doctor and etc. My language is not common with all of them. In fact, they help me and correct my dialogues"¹⁹.

Kiarostami used intelligent realistic elements to combine reality and imagination to address issues of modernity. His films are in complete contradiction with the policies of the Islamic cinema. Perhaps the experience of a revolution and a devastating war divides Iran among the nations, but the suppression of art and human rights will make people look for a coherent and ideal society.

Film critic *Jonathan Rosenbaum* says about *Kiarostami*'s films: "For me, *Kiarostami* is first of all a global filmmaker and secondarily an Iranian filmmaker. Even though I'm interested in learning about Iran through Iranian cinema, and his films are certainly a part of that, I feel that I go to his films to learn about the world, not just Iran. There are surely other Iranian filmmakers who could tell me more about Iran than he can, but I don't think that there are any other Iranian filmmakers now who could tell me as much about the world in general"²⁰.

¹⁹ Mihanparast, Ismail. *New world new cinema (Interviews with the Iran's Cinema Directors)*. First Edition, Tehran: Cheshmeh Publishing. 2008

²⁰ Rosenbaum, Jonathan. Saeed-Vafa, Mehrnaz. *Abbas Kiarostami: a dialogue between the authors*. Senses of cinema journal. Issue 17. November 2001

Social Realism and Asghar Farhadi (1972, Iran)

General Characteristics of Farhadi's cinema

The influences that Italy's cinema has placed as the most prominent cinema of social realism in the history of cinema can be traced back to Iran's cinema. With a general look at *Farhadi's* films, it is easy to find more features of social-realism films in his works. He takes the facts from the community and, by manipulating them, presents them to society. *Farhadi* has received two Academy Awards for best foreign language film for "A Separation" (2012) and "The Salesman" (2016), that makes him one of the few directors worldwide who have won Academy Award for best foreign language twice. In addition to using realistic stories and noticeable personalities, *Farhadi* works in the field of directing to further achieve this key element. The realistic elements in *Farhadi's* films are in summary: 1) Physical involvement in the films: The psychological justification of these scenes is more than the dramatic one due to its reliance on reality. 2) Subtle *mise-en-scène*: One of the effective solutions to the film's reality is the deliberate collision of frames and the approach of the camera to the characters which can help the more engaging of the viewer with the reality on the scene. 3) The principle of continuity in the realism of the scene, or in other words, the sinking of the viewer in the scene through a fast sequence of scenes, is one of the main reasons for the success of *Farhadi's* films. 4) In the framework of the narrative modeling, we conclude that the realistic question of films passes from an accidental point of view to gradually reveal its social subtext. "Is the world a good place to go on living?" ²¹.

Farhadi's directing method

Social realism in Italy was structurally adapted from classical cinema, but in the context of the story, they have opened a new field. The story of films is sometimes widespread in an accident, because casualties reflect real life better ²². *Farhadi's* scripts follow a great deal of classical structure and strongly rely on accidents and crashes. But *Farhadi*, unlike Italian realism, wants to put all events at the same level and avoid ups and downs. *Farhadi* with an incident storytelling, has been able to get closer to realism. The similarity in the narrative of *Farhadi's* films to Italian social realism is partly related to the open-ended film which makes the films closer to reality. Also, like many Italian directors, he uses neo-realist narrative practices such as the removal of important events. The social class in *Farhadi's* films is more like *Antonioni's* films than neorealism, contrary to neo-realism, which addressed the problems of the working class of the post-war Italian society.

²¹ Giles, Harvey. How Iran's greatest director makes art of moral ambiguity. The New York Times. January 2019

²² Thompson, Kristin. Bordwell, David. *Film art: an introduction*. Publisher: McGraw-Hill higher education; 4th edition. February 2014. P: 424-505

Like *Antonioni*, he criticizes the middle-class of the society involved in the moral crisis and shows how changing social conditions affects personal relationships. This effect is clearly obvious in “*Darbareye Elly*” (2009). In his films, characters are involved with their daily routines, and suddenly a crisis changes the circumstances. Although they appear to have a good relationship, but this relationship is a misleading, and their identity is revealed with an incident. As in the case of “*Darbareye Elly*”, the mysterious disappearance of a kindergarten teacher, *Elly*, during a picnic in the north of Iran is followed by a series of misadventures for her fellow travelers and the friendship of the them is dim. His cinema, like the tradition of Iranian cinema, has similarities to Italian cinema. If Italian filmmakers, after the war tried to portray the problems of society, *Farhadi's* cinema was also criticized the Iranian society in the course of time. The topics he employs are lies, secrecy, judgment, ignorance and self-conceit. The use of the camera on the hand, along with the sharp rhythm of the fast and sequential scenes, is another feature of *Farhadi's* work, which is also influenced by the cinema of Italy.

Another brilliant feature of *Farhadi's* films that are back to Italy is the mix of professional and non-professional actors. *Farhadi*, though, employs more professional actors. But, as *Bazin* says: “The basis of social realism is not skipping the professional actors. Rather, it's a rejection of the concept of super-star making, as well as a random mix of professional and non-professional actors. It's important that a professional actor does not have to play a role that is well-known”²³.

He says: “the non-professional actor cannot act as a professional actor because he does not know the formula, and in fact this is a professional actor who must coordinate himself with others”²⁴. The location in *Farhadi's* films, in contrast to the social realism of Italy which depicted the scenes of the city more often, is more in-house and apartment and is less referring to the relations within the out-side community. With a careful look at *Farhadi's* works, it can be seen that his works never fall into the intellectual works of a particular audience that distract him from the people of society. The reason for this is the complete recognition of the filmmaker from the cinema media and the society in which he lives. The use of new and completely touchable subjects by *Farhadi*, such as the lie and separation and murder that is affecting the present human community, not only causes the Iranian audience to be associated, but also the foreign audience is well connected with it. *Farhadi's* success, such as Italian social realism films, is due to the fact that his themes are rooted in the human relations of the entire world. Therefore, his films communicate with all audiences, regardless of cultural geography and language.

²³ Bazin, André. *What is cinema?* University of California Pres. Vol. 1 & 2 Hugh Gray, Trans., Ed. 2005.

²⁴ Mihanparast, Ismail. *New world new cinema (Interviews with the Iran's Cinema Directors)*. First Edition, Tehran: Cheshmeh Publishing. 2008

Conclusion

Social changes have a great impact in the culture and art, and many developments in these fields are due to social changes. In the realm of art, these developments are very effective and one of the most important branches of realism is determining social realism. Social-realism films that reflect society have been shaped by political-social conditions in the history of cinema or in response to existing conditions. With the outbreak of World War II and due to widespread political and social developments, the largest movement of cinema realism in Italy was formed.

The researchers point to Italy as the root of social realism in the cinema. It affected the cinema of countries with lacked national cinema and a desire to change. Iran's cinema belongs to these cinemas. After the war in Iran, restrictions, censorship, poverty, unemployment, and social discontent all attracted the attention of Iranian film makers. So, the serious move of social realism comes back to the post-war era, in which the filmmaker criticized the social conditions and crises that arose because of the war. With political and social changes and the emergence of popular critics in the 1980s, a blankness in Iranian cinema was felt that led to the formation of the social realism cinema in Iran.

Kiarostami's films, as the leader of social realism in Iran, were most humanistic tendencies in contrast to the violent world. His cinema was influenced by the style and ethics of Italian social realism, and many of its structural rules are tolerated by the cinema of Italy. The rise of the revolution affected the Iranian social realism. During the imposed war, the realist cinema turned to the war specifically. This movement resulted from several factors, like direct and immediate changes of a social reality as immigration from the war ²⁵. These films continued until the 90s.

On the other hand, at the end of this decade, due to the growth of urbanization and the rise of the middle class in society, the social difficulties were occurred, and the human relations between the people became more complicated.

In fact, this class was facing a crisis of identity and ethics to find a new definition. Therefore, the socially-deep-minded filmmakers, have produced social films with ethical issues. Because of this, in cinema of Iran, after the post-war period, the subject of films is often about anomalies and intolerance within the community and among the middle class. By making such films in the second millennium, a wave of social realism films began to dominate that the films of *Asghar Farhadi* are the widely-known example. The study of the character of *Farhadi's* films is the recognition of this wave. The study of his films shows that he is acting on the theme contrary to Italian social realism. The theme of *Farhadi's* films such as *Antonioni* is how social conditions affect people's relationships. This theme is not completely new in Iran's cinema, but the predominant ethical issue has started with *Farhadi's* films.

²⁵ Farasati, Massoud. *War and Peace*. Association of Revolutionary and Holy Defense Cinema. First Edition, Tehran. 2000

Farhadi's most important feature in his screenplay includes two positive points. First of all, it is up to date and with full knowledge of the conditions, concerns and problems in the relations of human beings, especially the middle class. The second is the style of story-telling and its new and fascinating stories.

In this context, he uses the classical structure of Italian social realism, and in some cases, such as the introduction, it deconstructs them somewhat differently. All his efforts in his films are more realistic and he tries to engage the audience with the film and make him to think. The open ends and the removal of some important events in his films also imitate Italian cinema due to the incitement of thinking and, therefore, becomes closer to realism. He tries to find out and mimic the common forms in this field by making his films closer to realism. *Farhadi* selects and artistically uses his films in the context of his goals, with full knowledge, in the possession of new stories and full awareness of the common forms in the Italian social realism cinema. These factors are the main factor behind the success of *Farhadi's* films inside and outside Iran.

All artistic movements have a social horizon and are produced in a certain period of time and in specific social conditions. We must admit that the expression of social issues is only in the realism movement. Within the theoretical framework of social realism, any human activity is shaped by sociological features. Social realism focuses on the unpleasant realities of contemporary life and sympathized with the people who are involved in that circumstances.

References

1. Bazin, A. (2005). *What is Cinema?* University of California Pres. Vol. 1 & 2 Hugh Gray, Trans., Ed.
2. Eftekhari, Z. (2007). *Study of the Origins of the Appearance of Neorealist-Critical Cinema in Iran after the Revolution.* Art Research, Tehran: Art University.
3. Farasati, M. (2000). *War and Peace.* Association of Revolutionary and Holy Defense Cinema. First Edition.
4. Giles, H. (2019). How Iran's greatest director makes art of moral ambiguity. *The New York Times.* January.
5. Hayward, S. (2013). *Cinema studies: The key concepts.* Publisher: Routledge; 4th edition. February.

6. Huaco, G. (1965). *Sociology of Film Art*. Publisher: Basic Books. October 1965.
7. Margulies, I. (2007). *Abbas Kiarostami*. Princeton University. Retrieved 23 February.
8. Mihanparast, I. (2008). *New world new cinema (Interviews with the Iran's Cinema Directors)*. First Edition, Tehran: Cheshmeh Publishing.
9. Mohammad Kashi, S. (2006). Realism in Iranian cinema. *Journal of the Moon of art*. No. 95, 2006.
10. Mudede, C. (1999). *Kiarostami's genius style. The stranger*.
11. Nowell-Smith, G. (1999). *The oxford history of world cinema*. Publisher: oxford University press. 17th edition. February.
12. Pakbaz, R. (2009). *Encyclopedia of Art*. Eighth Edition, Tehran: Contemporary Culture.
13. Rosenbaum, J. & Saeed-Vafa, M. (2001). *Abbas Kiarostami: a dialogue between the authors*. *Senses of cinema journal*. Issue 17. November 2001.
14. Talebi Nejad, A. (1998). *Analytical Date of the Post-Revolutionary Cinema*. Tehran: Farabi Publishing.
15. Talebi Nejad, A. (1998). *In the presence of the cinema*. First Printing, Tehran: Farabi Publishing.
16. Thompson, K. & Bordwell, D. (2014). *Film art: an introduction*. Publisher: McGraw-Hill; 4th edition. February 2014. P: 424-505.
17. Thompson, K. & Bordwel, D. (2010). *Storia del cinema*. Publisher: McGraw-Hill higher education; 9th edition. January.
18. Verdone, M. (1977). *Le avanguardie storiche del cinema*. Torino: Societa editrice internazionale.